

**“Intra operative Measurement Of Eustachian Tube Orifice And Its
Correlation With Post operative Surgical Outcome In CSOM Patients”**

Submitted by

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M.B.B.S.

Dissertation submitted to the

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In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

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In

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

Under the guidance of

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

%	Percentage
EAC	External auditory canal
TM	Tympanic Membrane
CSOM	Chronic suppurations otitis media
D/s	Discharge
HOH	Hard of hearing
ETS	Eustachian tube score
ETD	Eustachian tube diameter
TMM	Tubomanometry
SDVE	Slow motion dynamic video endoscopy

ABSTRACT

BACK GROUND:

WHO observed an overall CSOM prevalence of 7.8% in Indian population. ¹

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is the inflammation of the middle ear mucosa for a duration of more than two weeks that results in ear discharge. It is associated with hearing loss.²

Vital structures like internal carotid artery, facial nerve, jugular bulb, sigmoid sinus are present within the temporal bone.

Destruction of ossicles and attic capsule may occur in extensive cases of Cholesteatoma.

Early identification is needed to adopt the right surgical procedure and to

prevent hearing loss and complications. ⁹

By knowing the Intra operative Eustachian Tube diameter , we can find out the significance of Eustachian Tube size with the Post operative Graft Uptake.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1) Measurement of Eustachian tube size(intraoperative) in COM(Tubotympanic type)

2) Assessing treatment outcome of CSOM (tubotympanic type) in relation to Eustachian tube size .

METHODOLOGY:

7.1 SOURCE OF DATA

Patients satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria attending opd and of patients admitted to the department of otorhinolaryngology, BLDEU's SHRI B M PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA.

7.2 METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

- Preoperative examination of the patient including complete clinical history.
- Characteristics of patients including age, gender, residence.
- Detailed examination of the patient with emphasis on otoscopic findings is done to see the status of tympanic membrane and examination of nose , throat ,and oropharynx
- Patient will be subjected to investigations such as urine routine, blood routine examinations, impedance audiometry.
- Eustachian tube function will be assessed intraoperatively by measuring the size of Eustachian tube orifice.
- Thereafter in all the cases with chronic otitis media ,surgical outcome will be measured in relation to the size of Eustachian tube.

RESULTS:

In our study, we found a significant correlation between the Intra operative Eustachian Tube diameter and the post operative graft uptake with p value of 0.00

KEY WORDS

ETD- EUSTACHIAN TUBE DIAMETER

CSOM –Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media

INTRA op-Intra Operative Findings.

GRAFT- post operative graft uptake

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INTRODUCTION

WHO observed an overall CSOM prevalence of 7.8% in Indian population. ¹

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is the inflammation of the middle ear mucosa for a duration of more than two weeks that results in ear discharge. It is associated with hearing loss. ²

Eustachian Tube plays an important role in the the functioning of normal middle ear.

The 3 major functions of Eustachian Tube in middle ear are :

- (i) Protects sound pressure from nasopharynx .
- (ii) Helps in draining of middle ear secretions .
- (iii) Maintains equilibrium between air pressure in the middle ear and atmosphere.

Infection from the nasopharynx travels through the Eustachian Tube thereby resulting in the mucosal type of Chronic Otitis Media.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- 1) Measurement of Eustachian tube size (intraoperative) in COM (Tubotympanic type)
- 2) Assessing treatment outcome of CSOM (tubotympanic type) in relation to Eustachian tube size .

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

EUSTACHIAN TUBE ¹²

An auditory or pharyngotympanic tube is another name for it. The tube, which extends from the middle ear downward, forward, and medially, joins the tympanic cavity with the nasopharynx. In an average adult, its length is around 36 mm. There are two sections: a medial fibrocartilaginous part that enters the nasopharynx and a lateral bony posterior part that emerges from the tympanic cavity's anterior wall. There is respiratory mucosa lining the tube. The bony segment is 12 mm in length. The narrowest section, with a diameter of 2 mm, is the isthmus. Compared to adults, the tube is shorter, broader, and more horizontal in newborns.

THE EUSTACHIAN TUBE (E.T.)

- The nasopharynx and middle ear are connected by the dynamic Eustachian tube.
- It reaches its full size of approximately 36 mm by the time an individual reaches the age of seven. It has a 2 mm diameter where it has been flattened.
- It is twisted medially and forwards as it descends from the middle ear at 450 degrees.
- The respiratory mucosa of the tube is lined with mucous glands and goblet cells, and its floor is covered in ciliated epithelium.
- The mucosa is genuinely respiratory at the nasopharyngeal end, but as the tube continues to the middle ear, fewer goblet cells and glands are present, and the ciliary carpet is less dense.

The bony portion

- The anterior wall of the tympanic cavity gives rise to the bony lateral third.
- A cartilaginous section in the middle that accounts for two thirds of the tubal length. The isthmus, the narrowest cartilaginous section, is where the two halves unite.
- The osseous area is roughly 12 mm in length.
- Largest at the oval-shaped opening in the tympanic cavity's front wall.
- It passes through the petrous and squamous regions of the temporal bone before progressively narrowing to a diameter of no more than 0.5 mm at the isthmus.
- The roof is a thin plate of bone that divides the tube from the tensor tympani muscle above.
- The bony Eustachian tube may be impinged upon by the carotid canal, which is located medially.
- The tube is triangular in cross section, with the horizontal part.

The cartilaginous:

- The cartilaginous portion is roughly 24 mm in length .
- The cartilage forms a shorter lateral cartilaginous lamina and a longer medial cartilaginous lamina at its upper border, bending over to resemble an inverted "J."
- The cartilage ends close to the root of the medial pterygoid plate. The cartilage makes up the posteromedial wall, while fibrous tissue and cartilage make up the anterolateral wall.
- The cartilage's broader medial end protrudes into the nasopharynx, right under the nasal cavity, while the cartilage's apex is joined to the bony portion's isthmus.

In the nasopharynx:

- The tube in the nasopharynx opens between 1 and 1.25 centimeters behind and slightly below the inferior turbinate's posterior end.
- The torus encircles the entrance, which has an approximately triangular shape, from above and behind.
- The salpingopharyngeal fold extends from the pharyngeal wall to the bottom portion of the torus.
- The pharyngeal recess, also known as the Fossa of Rosenmuller (which is located behind the nasopharyngeal orifice of ET) is located behind the torus and is typically filled with tiny, but orderly, lymph nodes. It is the most typical location for nasopharyngeal cancer.

Fossa of Rossemuller is the area surrounding the tubal opening contain lymphoid tissue, which can be noticeable in young children.

Normally closed at rest, the tube opens when swallowing and yawning due to the action of the levator and, to a lesser extent, the tensor palate.

The main functions of the E.T. :

1. equalize the protective pressure of the air on either side of the tympanic membrane.
2. Permit the middle ear's fluids to drain.
3. Stop nasopharyngeal secretion reflux.

In addition to mechanical elements such as gravity and air pressure gradient, the following factors also affect middle ear secretion clearance:

- (i) the Eustachian tube mucociliary transport mechanism
- (ii) active tubal opening
- (iii) surface tension parameters.

Ostmann's pad of fat is fibrofatty tissue connected to the cartilaginous tube's membrane, particularly in the nasopharynx area.

It keeps the esophageal tube tight, preventing nasopharyngeal reflux.

The tube is longer, wider, and more horizontal in newborns and early children, which makes it easier for infections to travel to the middle ear.

MUSCLES ATTACHED TO THE EUSTACHIAN TUBE

The tensor palatini muscle:

1. Originates from the scaphoid bone wall and extends along the entire lateral cartilaginous lamina, which constitutes the upper part of the cartilaginous tube's front wall.
2. The muscle descends from these broad sources, converges at a short tendon that wraps around the pterygoid hamulus medially, and then extends out within the soft palate to connect fibers from the
3. Midline raphe.

Salpingopharyngeus:

1. Is a thin muscle that descends to merge with the palatopharyngeus and is linked to the inferior portion of the tube's cartilage close to its pharyngeal opening.

The levator palatini :

2. has a small number of fibers that come from the fascia that forms the upper portion of the carotid sheath and from the bottom surface of the petrous bone, right in front of the carotid entrance. These fibers also start from the lower surface of the cartilaginous tube.
3. Prior to crossing over to the medial side and expanding into the soft palate, it lies inferior to the tube.
4. The pharyngeal plexus supplies the levator palati and the salpingopharyngeus.

Arterial supply of E.T:

- The ascending pharyngeal artery.
- Middle meningeal arteries supply the Eustachian tube.
- Artery of pterygoid canal.

Venous drainage of E.T:

- The veins drain into the pharyngeal plexus

Lymph drainage of E.T:

- lymphatics pass to the retropharyngeal nodes.

Nerve supply of E.T:

1. Pharyngeal branch of the sphenopalatine ganglion (Vb) for Ostium
2. Tympanic plexus (IX) for bony part.

Methods of testing eustachian tube dysfunction :

1. Valsalva manoeuver
2. Toynbee manoeuver
3. Frenzel manoeuver
4. Segaliation
5. Politzerization
6. ET canulation
7. Manometric studies
8. Endoscopic examination of Tubal orifice
9. Contrast radiography
10. TYMPANOMETRY
11. CT
12. MRI
13. SONOTUBOMETRY
14. Eustachian tube dysfunction questionnaire (ETDQ-7)

Manometric testings (tympanometry, reflex decay tympanometry, ninestep inflation deflation test, modified inflation deflation test, forced response test and tubomanometry

In sonotubometry, sound is applied through a probe in the nose which is then measured in the external auditory canal and fluctuations are recorded during swallowing.

CHRONIC OTITIS MEDIA

Chronic otitis media (COM) is an inflammatory process in the middle ear space that results in long term or more often, permanent changes in the tympanic membrane including atelectasis, dimer formation, perforation, tympanosclerosis, retraction pocket development, or cholesteatoma ²⁰.

Chronic inactive otitis media with perforation :

Characterised by permanent perforation of tympanic membrane without inflammation of middle ear mucosa. There is thickening of lamina propria around the perforation as a result of fibrous tissue proliferation. This can cause migration of squamous epithelium into middle ear .

Chronic inactive otitis media with retraction pocket :

Retraction of the membrane occurs due to negative pressure in middle ear. A retraction pocket consists of the invagination of tympanic membrane into middle ear.

Chronic inactive otitis media with frequent reactivation :

In this, there will be episodes of reactivation or flare ups . It is due to a subclinical inflammation in the middle ear and the mastoid air cell system. The patient is able to return to a clinically inactive state after each flare up.

Chronic active otitis media with cholesteatoma:

Characterised by retention of keratinous debris. Lined by squamous epithelium. Matrix is covered by a layer of vascular subepithelial connective tissue. Cholesteatoma can cause bone resorption resulting in intra temporal and intra cranial complications.

TYMPANOPLASTY

It is a surgery for reconstruction of tympanic membrane.

Wullstein classification :

Type 1: Inspection of the middle ear and correction of the perforation wherein the ossicular chain is intact.

Type 2: Ossicular chain examination shows erosion of the malleus and therefore placement of graft over the intact incus and stapes.

Type 3: Ossicular chain examination shows erosion of malleus and incus, so that the graft is placed over the head of stapes.

Type 4: Ossicular chain examination shows presence of only footplate of stapes over which the graft is placed.

Type 5: Footplate of stapes is fixed. Graft is placed over the round window.

MIDDLE EAR RISK FACTOR INDEX :

The Middle Ear Risk Index (MERI) was devised by Kartush in 1994 to identify severity of disease preoperatively.

otological factor	maximum score
otorrhea	3
perforation	1
cholesteatoma	2
ossicular status	4
middle ear granulation	2
previous surgery	2
smoking	2

Indications of tympanoplasty:

1. Infection
2. Hearing loss
3. Social

Contraindications:

1. Cholesteatoma
2. Contralateral hearing
3. Bilateral perforations
4. Eustachian tube dysfunction

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA:

Study Design: Hospital based Prospective Study.

Study Duration: From November 2022 to June 2024

Sample Size: 55 patients.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

All cases of chronic suppurative otitis media (mucosal) attending to ENT opd from June 2022 to June 2024 getting operated in B.L.D.E (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, VIJAYAPURA.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- 1) Unwilling patients
- 2) Previously operated for csom .
- 3) Cases with traumatic perforation of tympanic membrane.
- 4) Congenital anomaly (Cleft Lip / Cleft Palate)
- 5) Atticoantral disease

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

- Preoperative examination of the patient including complete clinical history.
- Characteristics of patients including age, gender, residence,
- Detailed examination of the patient with emphasis on otoscopic findings is done to see the status of tympanic membrane and examination of nose , throat ,and oropharynx
- Patient will be subjected to investigations such as urine routine, blood routine examinations, PTA
- Intra Operatively Eustachian Tube Orifice diameter is measured with the help of Suction tips of different sizes.
- Post operatively ,the surgical outcome is assessed in the form of graft uptake 3 months after surgery.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Descriptive summary is done for all characters .Statistics of N, mean, median, IQR and standard deviation (SD) are used. For categorical data, the number and percentage will be used in the data summaries and is analyzed by Chi square test or Fishers exact test for association, comparison of means using, sensitivity, specificity and diagrammatic presentation.

By using the formula:

$$n = \frac{z^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

where

Z= z statistic at 5% level of significance

d is margin of error

p is maximum anticipated prevalence rate

If the p- value was less than (<0.05) , then the results were considered to be statistically significant.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

A hospital based prospective study was conducted with 55 patients who came to ENT department.

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE:

Out of 55 patients enrolled maximum patients were in between the age group of 20-50yrs

Age(Years)	No. of patients	Percentage
< 20	7	12.7
20 - 29	12	21.8
30 - 39	13	23.6
40 - 49	10	18.2
50 - 59	9	16.4
60+	4	7.3
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 1: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO AGE

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study 27 (49.1%) were females, 28 (50.9%) were males.

Gender	No. of patients	Percentage
Female	27	49.1
Male	28	50.9
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 2: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SEX:

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO EAR DISCHARGE:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , 31(56.4%) had right ear disease and 24(43.6%) had left ear disease.

Ear Discharge	No. of patients	Percentage
Right	31	56.4
Left	24	43.6
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 3: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO EAR DISCHARGE:

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO REDUCED HEARING:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , 48(87.3%) patients had complaint of reduced hearing , 7(12.7%) had no complaint of reduced hearing.

Reduced hearing	No. of patients	Percentage
Yes	48	87.3
No	7	12.7
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 4: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO REDUCED HEARING:

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO ACTIVE EAR DISCHARGE:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , all 55(100%) didn't have active ear discharge

EAC	No. of patients	Percentage
Clear	55	100.0
Discharge	0.0	0.0
Total	55	100.0

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO SIZE OF PERFORATION :

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , 11(20.0%) Patients had LCP , 19(34.5%) patients had MCP, 19(34.5%) patients had SCP, 6(10.9%) patients had subtotal perforation.

Tympanic membrane(size of perforation)	No. of patients	Percentage
LCP	11	20.0
MCP	19	34.5
SCP	19	34.5
Subtotal	6	10.9
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 5 : ACCORDING TO SIZE OF PERFORATION

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO RINNES TEST:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , all 55(100%) patients showed negative Rinnes test

Pre operative Rinnes	No. of patients	Percentage
Positive	0	0.0
Negative	55	100.0
Total	55	100.0

TABLE 8: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO WEBERS TEST:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study ,30 (54.5%) patients webers was lateralized to right ear and in 25(45.5%) patients webers lateralized to left ear .

Pre operative Webers	No. of patients	Percentage
Lateralized to right	30	54.5
Lateralized to left	25	45.5
Total	55	100.0

TABLE 9: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO DNS:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study ,3 (5.4%) patients had right DNS, 3(3.6%) Patients had left DNS , 50(90.9%)patients had no DNS.

Nose -DNS	No. of patients	Percentage
DNS to right	3	5.4
DNS to left	2	3.6
No DNS	50	90.9
Total	55	100.0

TABLE 10: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO OROPHARYNGEAL MASS /TONSIL:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study ,In all 55(100%) patients no oropharyngeal mass or tonsil hypertrophy was seen .

Oropharyngeal Mass / Tonsil	No. of patients	Percentage
Yes	0	0.0
No	55	100.0
Total	55	100.0

TABLE 11: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO INTRAOPERATIVE EUSTACHIAN TUBE DIAMETER:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study ,16 (29.1%) patients intraoperative Eustachian tube diameter was 5mm, followed by in 15 (27.3%)patients Eustachian tube diameter was 6mm seen in majority of patients followed by 9 (16.4%) patients with 4mm tube diameter and in 9(16.4%) patients with tube diameter 3mm was observed, remaining patients has 2mm and 1mm diameter as give in below table.

Intra operative Eustachian Tube Diameter(in mm)	No. of patients	Percentage (%)
1	2	3.6
2	3	5.5
3	9	16.4
4	9	16.4
5	16	29.1
6	15	27.3
7	1	1.8
Total	55	100

GRAPH 6: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO INTRAOPERATIVE EUSTACHIAN TUBE DIAMETER :

TABLE 12: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO POST OPERATIVE GRAFT UPTAKE:

Out of 55 patients enrolled in the study , 44(76.4%) patients post operative graft uptake was seen successfully, remaining 13(23.6%) patients graft uptake was not seen.

Post operative graft uptake	No. of patients	Percentage
Yes	42	76.4
No	13	23.6
Total	55	100.0

GRAPH 7: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO POST OPERATIVE GRAFT UPTAKE:

Statistics			
	Age	Duration of Ear discharge(years)	Intra operative Eustachian tube diameter(mm)
Mean	36.22	6.2	4.51
Median	35	5	5
Std. Deviation	14.637	5.502	1.426
Minimum	14	1	1
Maximum	69	25	7

TABLE 13: DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO POST OPERATIVE GRAFT UPTAKE AT 3 MONTHS :

Over all post operative graft uptake was seen in majority of patients with wider Eustachian tube diameter ranging between 3mm-6mm diameter with statistically significant p value of 0.00 (0.05)

Intra operative Eustachian tube diameter(mm) * Post operative garft uptake at 3 months

		Post operative garft uptake at 3 months		Total	
		no	yes		
Intra operative Eustachian tube diameter(mm) (Binned)	< 3		5	0	5
			38.5%	0.0%	9.1%
	3 - 5		8	26	34
			61.5%	61.9%	61.8%
	6+		0	16	16
			0.0%	38.1%	29.1%
Total			13	42	55
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests		
	Value	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.106	.000

P Value of 0.00 (<0.05) –statistically significant

TABLE 14 : DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO POST OPERATIVE GRAFT UPTAKE WITH SIZE OF PERFORATION:

Overall, post operatively better graft uptake's was seen in patients with MCP and SCP when compared to patients with LCP and Subtotal perforation .

Tympanic membrane * Post operative garft uptake at 3 months					
			Post operative garft uptake at 3 months		Total
			no	yes	
Tympanic membrane	LCP		4	7	11
			30.8%	16.7%	20.0%
	MCP		3	16	19
			23.1%	38.1%	34.5%
	SCP		1	18	19
			7.7%	42.9%	34.5%
	subtotal perforation		5	1	6
			38.5%	2.4%	10.9%
Total			13	42	55
			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests		
	Value	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	17.035	.001

Fig 1: Showing intraoperative Eustachian tube opening in middle ear

Fig 2: Showing intraoperative measurement of Eustachian tube

Fig 3: Varied sizes of Eustachian tube diameter

Intra -operative Eustachian Tube

7mm(wide)

5mm(normal)

Fig 4: Postoperative graft uptake at 3months

RESULTS (Post Operative Graft uptake)

Defect in graft

Intact graft

DISCUSSION

In our study, out of 55 patients post operative graft uptake was correlated with size of the Eustachian tube which was measured intraoperatively and found that patients with Eustachian tube diameter of size >3mm had good post operative graft uptake without any defects in graft .

In a study done by k Priya *et al*¹ , post operative graft uptake was compared with Eustachian tube function that was measured by Toynbee test, out of 100 Patients 78% had good ET fuction and results were reflected in good graft uptake.

In a study done by Cohn *et al*² , they had assessed Eustachian tube function with impedance audiometry , patient's with normal impedance showed 95% graft uptake, 75% graft uptake was seen in patients with impaired impedance , 69% graft uptake seen in patients with totally impaired impedance .

In a study done by gunjan *et al*¹¹, they have done Eustachian tube functional evaluation done in COM patients using impedance audiometry and dynamic slow motion video endoscopy , patients with good DSVE and IA , good preoperative function is important for better surgical outcomes.

In a study done by Ruixiang Li *et al*¹⁰ 2020 , post operative graft uptake in type 1 tympanoplasty was correlate with Eustachian tube function that was ETS includes objective tubomanometry and subjective valsalva and Toynbee maneuvers. In there study both cases and controls groups divide based on ETS both group had good post operative graft uptake .

In a study done by yak up *et al*.⁹ in 2016 , effect of angle and length of ET on the success of cartilage tympanoplasty and concluded that neither angle or length effects the postoperative graft uptake.

CONCLUSION

In our study , we found that there is a association between the Eustachian tube diameter and post operative graft uptake. In Patients with Eustachian tube diameter of $<3\text{mm}$ there was defect in post operative graft uptake, where as patients with Eustachian tube diameter of $>3\text{mm}$ had no post operative defect in graft.

Majority of the studies were done based on functional status of Eustachian tube diameter. Further studies are advised to assess the diameter of Eustachian tube in larger sample size to establish its value.

SUMMARY

The study “Intra operative Measurement Of Eustachian Tube Orifice And Its Correlation With Post operative Surgical Outcome in CSOM Patients”

was done in Shri B M Patil Medical college, hospital and research centre, Vijayapura during the period of November 2022 to June 2024.

A total of 55 patients were selected based on the inclusion criteria for the study to find out postoperative graft uptake based upon the size of Eustachian tube diameter measured intraoperatively. The following observations were noted:

1. Of the 55 cases, maximum patients were in between the age group of 20-50yrs
2. Of the 55 cases , 27 (49.1%) were females, 28 (50.9%) were males.
3. Of the 55 cases , 31(56.4%) had right ear disease and 24(43.6%) had left ear disease.
4. Of the 55 cases , 48(87.3%) patients had complaint of reduced hearing , 7(12.7%) had no complaint of reduced hearing.
5. Of the 55 cases , all 55(100%) didn't have active ear discharge
6. Of the 55 cases , 11(20.0%) Patients had LCP , 19(34.5%) patients had MCP, 19(34.5%) patients had SCP, 6(10.9%) patients had subtotal perforation.
7. Of the 55 cases , all 55(100%) patients showed positive Rinnes test
8. Of the 55 cases , 30 (54.5%) patients webbers was lateralized to right ear in 25(45.5%) patients webbers lateralized to left ear .
9. Of the 55 cases, 3 (5.4%) patients had right DNS, 3(3.6%) Patients had left DNS , 50(90.9%)patients had no DNS.

10. Of the 55 cases , In all 55(100%) patients no oropharyngeal mass or tonsil hypertrophy was seen .
11. Of the 55 cases, 44(76.4%) patients post operative graft uptake was seen successfully, remaining 13(23.6%) patients graft uptake was not seen.
12. Of the 55 cases ,16 (29.1%) patients intraoperative Eustachian tube diameter was 5mm, followed by in 15 (27.3%)patients Eustachian tube diameter was 6mm seen in majority of patients followed by 9 (16.4%) patients with 4mm tube diameter and in 9(16.4%) patients with tube diameter 3mm was observed, remaining patients has 2mm and 1mm diameter as give in below table.
13. Over all post operative graft uptake was seen in majority of patients with wider Eustachian tube diameter raging between 3mm-6mm diameter with statistically significant p value of 0.00 (0.05)
14. Overall, post operatively better graft uptake's was seen in patients with MCP and SCP when compared to patients with LCP and Subtotal perforation .

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ANNEXURE-1

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)
The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 708/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "INTRA OPERATIVE MEASUREMENT OF EUSTACHIAN TUBE LUMEN ORIFICE AND ITS CORRELATION WITH POSTOPERATIVE SURGICAL OUTCOME".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Mohan Raj.

NAME OF THE GUIDE : Dr R N Karadi, Professor, Dept. of ENT.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)

Dr. Akram A. Nalkwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethical Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura, Shri B. M. Patil Medical College

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutination

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.
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ANNEXURE-II

PROFORMA

SCHEME OF CASE TAKING

1) NAME: CASE NO:

2) AGE: IP NO:

3) SEX: DOA:

4) RELIGION: DOS:

5) OCCUPATION: DOD:

6) RESIDENCE:

7) CHIEF COMPLAINTS:

8) HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS:

9) PAST HISTORY:

10) FAMILY HISTORY:

11) GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

12) VITALS

PR:

BP:

RR:

Temp:

13) OTHER SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION:

14) LOCAL EXAMINATION

- EAR Right Left
 - Pinna
 - Pre auricular area
 - Post auricular area
 - External auditory canal

- Tympanic membrane Right Left">
 - Pars Tensa

 - Pars flaccida

- Mastoid Tenderness
- Fistula sign
- Tragal Tenderness
- Facial nerve function

- Nystagmus
- Tuning Fork test
 - Rinnes
 - Webers
 - ABC

- NOSE

- ORAL CAVITY

- OROPHARYNX

15) FINAL DIAGNOSIS:

16) INVESTIGATION:

Pre operative Impedance audiometry

Post operative Impedance audiometry

17) Size of Eustachian tube intra-operatively

18) FINAL DIAGNOSIS:

19) COMMENTS:

ANNEXURE-III

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

**BLDE (Deemed to be university) SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL
COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA- 586103**

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

**“Intra operative Measurement Of Eustachian Tube Orifice And Its
Correlation With Post operative Surgical Outcome in CSOM Patients”**

PG STUDENT

- Dr. G.MOHAN RAAJ

DEPARTMENT OF

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

PG GUIDE

- Dr. R.N.KARADI

PROFESSOR AND HOD

DEPARTMENT OF

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE

HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,

VIJAYAPUR, KARNATAKA– 586103

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her.

1) PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

2) PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received I will be asked series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this study

3) RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

4) BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to the patients survival and better outcome.

5) CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of Hospital records and will be subject to the confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigator's research file and

identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no name will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

6) REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at anytime.

DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during the study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

7) REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ may terminate my participation in the study after he has

explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist, if this is appropriate.

8) INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in patient's own language.

Dr. DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ

Date

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that Dr. DR. G.MOHAN RAAJ has explained to me the purpose of research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language.

I have read and I understand this consent form. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date

Witness to signature

Date

ANNEXURE-IV

KEY TO MASTER CHART

ABBREVIATIONS IN MASTERCHART

- 1.EAC- EXTERNAL AUDIOTORY CANAL
2. TM -TYMPANIC MEMBRANE
3. RT- RIGHT
4. LT- LEFT
5. D/S – DISCHARGE
6. DNS- DEVIATED NASAL SEPTUM
7. SCP- SMALL CENTRAL PERFORATION
8. MCP- MEDIUM CENTRAL PERFORATION
9. LCP- LARGE CENTRAL PERFORATION
- 10.ETD-EUSTACHIAN TUBE DIAMETER
11. ET- EUSTACHIAN TUBE
12. HOH-HARD OF HEARING

ANNEXURE-V**MASTERCHART**

Sno	Name	Ip No	Sex	Ag	RT Ear (d/s)	Lt ear (d/s)	Duration of d/s (in)	HOH	EAC	TI	Rinn	Weber's	Nose-DNS	Oropharyngeal mass/ Tonsil	Safe co	Intra op- EDD(rr)	ET- any pathological	Post-op graft uptake (3 months)
1	Lakshman	280064	Male	31	yes	no	6	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
2	Imtiyaz	287427	Female	28	yes	no	2	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes
3	Bebibai	305014	Female	50	yes	no	10	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to right	rt DNS	no	+	6	no	yes
4	Neelamma	346811	Female	21	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	3	no	no
5	Rajashri	341921	Female	35	No	yes	3	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
6	Sachin	376081	Male	18	Yes	no	1	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
7	Surekha	292653	Female	40	yes	no	7	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	lt DNS	no	+	2	no	no
8	Sangamesh	201465	Male	22	yes	no	4	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
9	Gurubasappa	420227	Male	21	No	yes	3	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	7	no	yes
10	Roopsingh	433790	Male	41	No	yes	25	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	1	no	no
11	Borava	418021	Female	69	No	yes	10	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	3	no	no
12	Ashwini	429823	Female	26	yes	no	2	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	rt DNS	no	+	6	no	yes
13	Akshata	41509	Female	25	Yes	no	1	no	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
14	Ravindra	55766	Male	50	yes	no	20	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
15	Ashwini	59318	Female	23	No	yes	2	no	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
16	Pradeep	64217	Male	31	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	rt DNS	no	+	2	no	no
17	Shivraj	64212	Male	47	yes	no	10	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
18	Pushpavati	67693	Female	56	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	3	no	yes
19	Gouri	60649	Female	44	No	yes	3	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
20	Bismilla	57083	Female	49	No	yes	5	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	1	no	no
21	Mukkanna	407249	Male	45	yes	no	15	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
22	Akshatha	73161	Female	32	yes	no	4	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
23	Omkar	81381	Male	40	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	lt DNS	no	+	5	no	yes
24	Hemanth	86981	Male	23	yes	no	2	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	3	no	no
25	Bhimavva	98713	Female	65	yes	no	15	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
26	Pooja	408263	Female	22	No	yes	2	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	4	no	yes
27	Harish	102263	Male	35	No	yes	12	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
28	Yallappa	102246	Male	64	yes	no	10	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	3	no	no
29	Vijayalakshmi	94026	Female	30	Yes	no	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
30	Lokesh	103637	Male	35	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
31	Bausab	113144	Male	60	yes	no	10	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	3	no	no
32	Shaila	103625	Female	34	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	4	no	yes
33	Jyoti Kori	117901	Female	56	No	yes	10	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
34	Laxman	128548	Male	51	yes	no	5	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
35	Raviraj	121473	Male	33	yes	no	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
36	Gangaram	140025	Male	45	yes	no	3	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes
37	Shivanand	156645	Male	15	No	yes	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
38	Raghavendra	127740	Male	40	yes	no	3	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes
39	Rohit	128082	Male	15	No	yes	3	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
40	Sharanamma	184912	Female	36	yes	no	6	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
41	Kashinath	1656213	Male	17	yes	no	2	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
42	Rihan	191643	Male	15	Yes	no	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
43	Fatima	158047	Female	30	yes	no	8	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	3	no	no
44	Sujata	187481	Female	38	No	yes	10	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
45	Mallamma	192684	Female	50	No	yes	18	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	3	no	no
46	Shantamma	207791	Female	43	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
47	Sitamma	207987	Female	24	Yes	no	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes
48	Veena	204477	Female	22	No	yes	3	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	5	no	yes
49	Aditya	214550	Male	14	Yes	no	1	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes
50	Danamma	230941	Female	52	yes	no	20	yes	clear	subt	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	2	no	no
51	Krishna	214264	Male	31	yes	no	6	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	4	no	yes
52	Shravan	354583	Male	57	No	yes	10	yes	clear	LCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	3	no	no
53	Rudramma	365671	Female	55	No	yes	5	yes	clear	MCP	-ve	lat to left	no	no	+	6	no	yes
54	Vinodkumar	373801	Male	23	yes	no	2	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	5	no	yes
55	Sampath	385195	Male	18	yes	no	2	yes	clear	SCP	-ve	lat to right	no	no	+	6	no	yes